

TABLE I—NERNST CONCENTRATION RANGE (IN MOLARITY) WITH DIFFERENT MEMBRANES FOR SEVERAL MONO AND DIVALENT CATIONS IN VARIOUS SOLVENT COMPOSITIONS

Material used as membrane	Of the Nernst concentration range, the minima was kept at $1 \times 10^{-4}M$ and the maxima ($10^{-2}M$) for different cations					
	H ⁺	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Ca ⁺⁺	Zn ⁺⁺	Mg ⁺⁺
i) Aqueous solution						
Ca oxalate	2.0	1.2	1.2	0.9	0.6	0.6
NH ₄ "	1.0	0.9	0.9	0.6	0.4	0.4
Uranyl "	0.6	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.08	0.8
Mixed "	2.0	1.0	1.0	0.9	0.6	0.6
ii) 20 weight % ethanol+ 80 weight % water						
Ca oxalate	2.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.8	0.8
NH ₄ "	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.4
Uranyl "	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.03	—	—
Mixed "	1.6	0.8	0.8	0.9	0.6	0.6

To understand the functioning of these materials as electrodes, it is necessary to consider their interfaces. Ion exchange reaction with these precipitates seems⁹ to be remote. The potential generation across these membranes possibly stems from the preferential adsorption of ions from solution on membrane interfaces as similar observations were made with BaSO₄ interface⁸.

References

1. H. J. C. TENDELOO, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1936, 113, 333.
2. H. DANIEL and K. HUTSCHNEKER, *Chimia*, 1955, 9, 49.
3. B. E. CONWAY, *Electrochemical Data*, Elsevier Publ. 1952, p. 103.
4. A. I. VOGEL, *Quantitative Inorganic Analysis*, Longmans Green & Co. 1962, p. 294.
5. L. M. ANDRIETH, *Inorganic Synthesis*, Vol. III, McGraw-Hill Book Co. 1950, p. 166.
6. M. ADHIKARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 373.
7. M. ADHIKARI, and G. G. BISWAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 399.
8. H. R. KRUYT, *Colloid Sci.*, Vol. I, Elsevier Publ. 1952, 175.

Phenyl Pyruvic Acid-2-Quinolyldiazone : A Reagent for Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper

MOHAN KATYAL*, S.K. KUNDRA, D. P. GOEL* & R.P. SINGH

*St. Stephen's College, Delhi 11007, and Chemistry Department, University of Delhi, Delhi 110007

Manuscript received 6 July 1973 ; revised 17 October 1973 ; accepted 11 December 1973

THE physiologically active substituted hydrazones are of immense importance for treatment of many diseases. In the last decade, a large number of hydrazones containing the atomic grouping

H

—N=C—C=N—N—C=N—

have been introduced as selective and sensitive reagents for determination of copper and other metals. More important amongst these are pyridine-2-aldehyde-2-pyridylhydrazone¹⁻⁴, pyridine-2-aldehyde-2-quinolyldiazone⁵⁻⁷, quinoline-2-aldehyde-2-quinolyldiazone^{8,9} and-2-benzoylpyri-

dine-2-pyridylhydrazone¹⁰. It was thought worthwhile to replace one of the nitrogen atoms of the hydrazones with a more electronegative atom like oxygen and thereby to improve the chelating characteristics of the compounds. Keeping this in view, the new hydrazone phenyl pyruvic acid-2-quinolyldiazone (I), abbreviated as PPA-QH, was synthesised and put to analytical use.

Cupric ions react with PPA-QH forming a deep yellow coloured complex soluble in 50% ethanol. Based on this colour reaction a sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method has been developed for copper.

Experimental

To synthesise PPA-QH, equimolar amounts of phenyl pyruvic acid and quinolyldiazine were taken in minimum amount of ethanol and refluxed for 5 hr. The product that separated on cooling was dried and recrystallised from alcohol to obtain yellow flakes melting at 240°. (C₁₈H₁₅N₃O₂ requires: C, 70.82%; H, 4.92%; N, 13.77%. Found : C, 69.83%; H, 4.68%; N, 13.20%).

Absorbance measurements were made with a Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer and pH of the solutions were checked using a Metrohm pH meter, type E-350.

To prepare $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution, 305 mg of PPA-QH were dissolved in 1 l of ethanol. The stock solution of copper was prepared using AnalaR (B.D.H.) grade CuSO₄ · 5H₂O. Buffer solutions were prepared by mixing appropriate amounts of sodium hydroxide with potassium hydrogen phosphate solution.

Results and Observations

The reagent solution (in ethanol) is light yellow in colour, having absorption maximum at 290 nm, with

NOTES

corresponding molar absorptivity 9.1×10^3 . The complex is deep yellow in colour with an absorption maximum at 450 nm which remains unaltered irrespective of the molar ratio of the components of the solution. This indicates the presence of only one complex in the solution under the conditions of study. The absorption by the reagent is also considerable at λ_{max} of the complex (450 nm); this necessitated the use of reagent blank in the subsequent study. The absorbance vs. pH plot shows that the absorption of the complex remains maximum and constant between pH 9.5 and 12.2. Thus a pH around 10.5 was kept for spectrophotometric study. The absorption of the reagent remains practically unaltered in the pH range under investigation. The mole-ratio plot shows that two moles of PPA-QH per mole of copper are sufficient for full colour development; thus indicating that the metal and the ligand are present in 1:2 ratio in the complex. This was also confirmed by the method of continuous variations.

The system adheres to Beer's law up to 2.5 γ /ml of copper concentration and its sensitivity is 0.002 γ Cu/cm² for 0.001 absorbance. The value for its molecular extinction coefficient is calculated to be 3.15×10^4 .

Procedure for Determination of Copper: Take a suitable aliquot of copper solution (up to 25 γ /ml) in a 10 ml volumetric flask, add sufficient excess (nearly 10 to 15 times the molar excess of copper solution) of PPA-QH solution (in ethanol), 2 ml of buffer solution (pH around 10.5) followed by alcohol and water so that the final solution contains 50% (v/v) alcohol. Measure the absorbance at 450 nm against a reagent blank prepared under similar conditions.

Extraction Procedure in Presence of Interfering Ions: In presence of sodium perchlorate the complex is sufficiently extractable in *n*-butanol. The extractability in chloroform is poor. To determine copper in presence of interfering ions, the copper complex may be extracted. To a suitable aliquot of copper solution, add 10 to 15 molar excess of PPA-QH solution (in alcohol), 2 ml of buffer (to adjust pH around 10.5) and 2.5 ml of 50% (w/v) sodium perchlorate solution. The alcohol content of the solution is slowly evaporated on a water bath and the volume is made up to 10 ml with water. The solution is shaken with 10 ml of *n*-butanol for 1 hr. The absorbance of the organic layer is measured at 450 nm against a reagent blank prepared under identical conditions.

Interferences

Many of the ions precipitate at the high pH which is used here for studying copper complex with PPA-QH. To study the effect of foreign ions on the determination of copper using this reagent, the precipitated species, if any, is either centrifuged off or the extraction procedure adopted as outlined above, and the absorbance of the decanted or extracted solution is measured at 450 nm. The amounts of foreign ions (in γ /ml) tolerated in estimation of 0.5 γ /ml of copper at pH 10.5 are: 100 γ /ml of each of CH_3COO^- , NO_2^- , F^- , I^- , SO_4^{2-} , SO_3^{2-} , citrate, tartrate, BO_3^{3-} , Ag^+ , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , As^{3+} , Sb^{3+} , Sn^{2+} , Ce^{4+} , Th^{4+} , and

UO_2^{2+} ; 50 γ /ml of each of NO_3^- , Cl^- , Br^- , Al^{3+} and Mo^{6+} ; 25 γ /ml of each of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , and Ni^{2+} ; and 2 to 4 γ /ml of each of platinum metals.

Copper was successfully determined in a number of alloys viz., brass, gun metal and BCS 180 cupronickel. Traces of copper were correctly estimated when added to cadmium and zinc acetates (2 to 5 γ /25 ml).

Discussion

The sensitivity of the present reagent towards detection and determination of copper is excellent and is comparable to other tridentate hydrazones. Amongst the earlier developed hydrazones, quinoline-2-aldehyde-2-quinolyldiazone^{8,9} having the most extended π -bonding system seems to be the most sensitive for copper. The values for its copper complex are 4.7×10^4 (in nitrobenzene) and 5.8×10^4 (in benzene) while that of copper-PPA-QH complex is 3.15×10^4 . The drawback of the reagent lies in its use at high pH where many other ions are also precipitated, thus making the centrifugation or extraction necessary.

Acknowledgement

The present work is done under the scheme 'Multidentate Chelating Agents-Hydrazones', for which the authors are grateful to the University Grants Commission. The authors are also thankful to Dr. B. S. Garg for useful suggestions.

References

1. A. J. CAMERON, N. A. GIBSON and R. ROPER., *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1963, 29, 73.
2. M. L. HEIT and D. E. RYAN., *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1965, 32, 448.
3. M. A. QUDDUS and C. F. BELL., *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1968, 42, 503.
4. A. J. CAMERON and N. A. GIBSON., *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1968, 40, 413.
5. M. L. HEIT and D. E. RYAN., *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1966, 34, 407.
6. R. E. JENSEN and R. T. PFLAUM., *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1967, 37, 397.
7. S. P. SINGHAL and D. E. RYAN., *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1967, 37, 91.
8. G. G. SIMS and D. E. RYAN., *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1969, 44, 139.
9. J. ABRAHAM, M. WINPE and D. E. RYAN., *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1969, 48, 431.
10. J. E. GOING and R. T. PFLAUM., *Anal. Chem.*, 1970, 42, 1098.

Polarographic Determination of the Composition and Formation Constant of the Aspirinato-molybdenum (VI) Complex

P. C. JAIN and S. P. BANERJEE

Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar, Saugar

Manuscript received 12 January 1971; Accepted 8 February 1974

ASPIRIN (acetyl salicylic acid), a derivative of salicylic acid is well known as an effective chelating agent. Extensive work has been done on a number of metal chelates of aspirin. Aspirin complex with rubidium¹ has been reported in literature. Sahu and Bhattacharya² have investigated thallos complex of aspirin by conductometric measurements. Gour, *et al.*³ have investigated indium-aspirin anion system polarographically and found various complex species in solution.